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Community contribution policy and GitHub App

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Executive Summary

This report describes the *community contribution policy* (hereinafter referred to as *Policy*) and the *Bot* (currently implemented as a [GitHub App](#) but can be extended to also service GitLab) that is used for building and deploying software for/to the shared software stack (EESSI).

The purpose of the Policy is to enable anyone to request an addition of a software package to the shared software stack provided by EESSI while making sure that key requirements of the shared software stack are retained.

The Bot is a service designed to facilitate Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) workflows and enables effective collaboration among maintainers and contributors of the shared software stack, guided by the policy.

The main concerns for the policy are: *What software can be contributed?* and *How shall the software be built and tested?*. It contains eight clearly defined rules:

1. Software must be freely redistributable software, and preferably open source;
2. Software being added must be built and deployed by the bot;
3. Software must be built and installed with [EasyBuild](#);
4. The compiler toolchain used must be supported by EasyBuild;
5. A recent toolchain should be used;
6. Recent software versions are preferred;
7. The software should work on all CPU targets supported by EESSI version being targeted;
8. It should be possible to test the built software packages being added using the EESSI test suite.

The current version of the policy is presented in Section 2.

Section 3 provides an overview of various aspects of the Bot including

- the design goals for the Bot (Section 3.1),
- an overview of the capabilities of the Bot (Section 3.2),
- how the Bot interfaces with the GitHub repositories of European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI) (Section 3.3),
- the user interface for the Bot (Section 3.4),
- how the Bot is installed and configured (Section 3.5),
- documentation of the Bot and additional tooling available (Section 3.6).

The Bot is a key tool to create and maintain a shared software stack that is optimized for various CPU microarchitectures with limited human effort intervention. It combines automated CI/CD workflows to build and deploy software artifacts with human oversight to ensure we maintain the high quality of the shared software stacks. Development of the Bot has resulted in three releases all being publicly available. In June 2023, we have started using the Bot to build and deploy software for the shared software stack. Since then, we have continuously refined the Bot by developing additional features and fixing bugs that were revealed by its users. Key statistics for the use of the Bot until late November 2023 are:

- At the time of writing (December, 2023), 13 contributors have used the bot, including two external to the MultiXscale project ([Square Kilometre Array Observatory \(SKAO\)](#)) and [Norwegian Environment for Scientific Software Installations \(NESSI\)](#));
- 70 pull requests for adding software to the EESSI stacks were handled;
- Roughly 500 software installations were built and deployed into the shared software stack (so in total, about 4,000 software installations were built for the 8 CPU microarchitectures currently supported by EESSI);
- Over 2,000 build jobs were run, where each job builds the software being added for a specific CPU microarchitecture, which can involve building multiple software packages (this includes repeated builds to address build failures).

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable provides a brief overview of the *community contribution policy* (frequently referred to as the *Policy* in this document) and the design of the *Bot*. Both components are being developed publicly and made available under Open Source licenses. Their development processes follow established procedures in the Open Source community with issues, pull requests, and peer review. Extensive documentation about the use of the *Bot* is available at the [EESSI documentation](#). Progress of the development and future directions were and will be openly discussed on the [EESSI Slack](#) and [EESSI monthly update meetings](#) as well as regular (virtual) development meetings focusing on the development of the Bot. The code of the implementation of the Bot as a GitHub App is developed in the GitHub repository [EESSI/eessi-bot-software-layer](#). Example uses of the Bot are openly available via dozens of [pull requests to the EESSI/software-layer repository](#).

1.2 Target audience

The *community contribution policy* is intended for EESSI contributors and maintainers. Contributors should know how EESSI is designed and how software is added to EESSI. Maintainers need to have in-depth knowledge about [EESSI](#), [EasyBuild](#) and the [Bot](#). It is noted that, although the policy and the Bot have been successfully used to add hundreds of software packages to multiple software stacks, we expect that their development will continue to implement new features and improvements to take feedback from contributors and maintainers into account.

1.3 Report outline

In Section 2, we introduce the initial version of the *community contribution policy*. Section 3 provides a high-level overview of the Bot. It discusses its design goals, its main workflow implementing CI/CD, the interface to repositories, how contributors can interact with the Bot, tooling to facilitate the debugging of failed build jobs as well as an overview of available documentation. We conclude in Section 4, summarizing the results and providing an outlook to future work.

2 Community contribution policy

2.1 Goals of the community contribution policy

The *community contribution policy* is aimed at enabling anyone to contribute any software to the shared software stacks provided that certain requirements are met. These requirements help ensure the high-quality of the software running with high-performance across a wide range of hardware.

2.2 Published community contribution policy

The *community contribution policy* was published on November 9, 2023 and made publicly available at [EESSI documentation / contribution policy](#). See below for a copy of the policy at the time of writing (December, 2023). The policy is inspired by successfully building an extensive pilot version of the shared software stack and also by experiences made in building a community around EasyBuild. All additions made to the currently latest version of the shared software stack (2023.06) comply with this policy.

Contribution policy

(version v0.1.0 - updated 9 Nov 2023)

Note

This policy is subject to change, please check back regularly.

Purpose

The purpose of this contribution policy is to provide guidelines for [adding software](#) to EESSI.

It informs about what requirements must be met in order for software to be eligible for inclusion in the EESSI software layer.

Requirements

The following requirements must be taken into account when adding software to EESSI.

Note that additional restrictions may apply in specific cases that are currently not covered explicitly by this policy.

i) Freely redistributable software

Only **freely redistributable software** can be added to the EESSI repository, and we strongly prefer including only **open source software** in EESSI.

Make sure that you are aware of the relevant software licenses, and that redistribution of the software you want to add to EESSI is allowed.

For more information about a specific software license, see the [SPDX license list](#).

Note

We intend to automatically verify that this requirement is met, by requiring that the [SPDX license identifier](#) is provided for all software included in EESSI.

ii) Built by the Bot

All software included in the EESSI repository *must* be **built autonomously** by [our Bot](#).

For more information, see our [semi-automatic software installation procedure](#).

iii) Built and installed with EasyBuild

We currently require that all software installations in EESSI are **built and installed using EasyBuild**.

We strongly prefer that the [latest release of EasyBuild](#) that is available at the time is used to add software to EESSI.

The use of `--from-pr` and `--include-easyblocks-from-pr` to pull in changes to EasyBuild that are required to make the installation work correctly in EESSI is allowed, but only if that is strictly required (that is, if those changes are not included yet in the latest EasyBuild release).

iv) Supported compiler toolchain

A **compiler toolchain that is still supported** by the latest EasyBuild *must* be used for building the software. For more information on supported toolchains, see the [EasyBuild toolchain support policy](#).

v) Recent toolchain versions

We strongly prefer adding software to EESSI that was built with a **recent compiler toolchain**.

When adding software to a particular version of EESSI, you should *use a toolchain version that is already installed*.

If you would like to see an additional toolchain version being added to a particular version of EESSI, please [open a support request](#) for this, and motivate your request.

vi) Recent software versions

We strongly prefer adding sufficiently **recent software versions** to EESSI.

If you would like to add older software versions, please clearly motivate the need for this in your contribution.

vii) CPU targets

Software that is added to EESSI *should work on all supported CPU targets*.

Exceptions to this requirement are allowed if technical problems that can not be resolved with reasonable effort prevent the installation of the software for specific CPU targets.

viii) Testing

We should be able to test the software installations via the [EESSI test suite](#), in particular for software applications and user-facing tools.

Ideally one or more tests are available that verify that the software is functionally correct, and that it (still) performs well.

Tests that are run during the software installation procedure as performed by EasyBuild *must* pass. Exceptions can be made if only a small subset of tests fail for specific CPU targets, as long as these exceptions are tracked and an effort is made to assess the impact of those failing tests.

It should be possible to run a minimal *smoke test* for the software included in EESSI, for example using EasyBuild's `--sanity-check-only` feature.

Note

The [EESSI test suite](#) is still in active development, and currently only has a minimal set of tests available.

When the test suite is more mature, this requirement will be enforced more strictly.

Changelog

v0.1.0 (9 Nov 2023)

- initial contribution policy

Note, in requirement *i*) the term **freely redistributable software** is deliberately used to be able to include software that may be redistributed but is not available under an open source license. [CUDA](#) (a closed source platform for enabling parallel computing on GPUs) is a prominent example of such a software package.

3 The Bot

This section provides an overview of the *Bot*, which in its current implementation supports GitHub as a [GitHub App](#) and can be extended to also support, for example, GitLab. We list the design goals for the Bot (Section 3.1), introduce its main workflow and tasks (Section 3.2), describe its interfaces to GitHub repositories (Section 3.3), provide information on its user interface (Section 3.4) and its installation and configuration (Section 3.5), and discuss tools for debugging as well as the documentation that is publicly available (Section 3.6).

3.1 Design goals for the Bot

We briefly list the design goals for the Bot which implements a CI/CD workflow that facilitates building scientific software for a wide range of HPC systems.

- Highly automate the build and deployment procedure to reduce human effort and to improve repeatability of the software installations;
- Allow for human oversight;
- Build software packages for the supported CPU microarchitectures;
- Ensure high quality of the built software via various levels of testing;
- Facilitate a high degree of configurability such that various distributed resources (Slurm-based clusters) with different configurations and environments may be used;
- Make the Bot as agnostic as possible to what it builds (thus it is more likely that it may be used for other scenarios such as EESSI-like stacks or local software stacks);
- Provide tooling to support debugging failing builds.

3.2 Overview of the Bot

Fig. 1 illustrates the workflow for adding software to the shared software stack. While that – adding software to the shared software stack provided by EESSI – is the primary use case for the Bot, there may be others such as building and deploying the compatibility layer of EESSI, or building software for a stack managed locally on a cluster. Thus, the Bot enables flexible continuous integration / continuous deployment CI/CD workflows.

The main approach in all these use cases is, that a Git repository defines which software installations a software stack shall contain and provides basic tools and scripts to add software on top of the existing software stack. Git repository hosting platforms such as GitHub and GitLab emit events that are triggered automatically by actions taken in a repository. The Bot can subscribe to such events via a webhook. The current release of the Bot (v0.2.0) reacts on two types of events from GitHub: (1) a pull request event, and (2) an issue comment event. Each event contains information that is then used for processing the event. Example information are: who opened the pull request, who created the issue comment, to which repository and branch the pull request was opened, the content of the issue comment, or an action for the pull request (such as labeled, closed, etc).

Depending on the type of the event, the Bot will respond with information about its configuration, create jobs for software to be built, or upload tarballs containing built software packages to a storage service. The Bot also needs to monitor the jobs it has created and to process their status changes. The two most important tasks of the Bot are

Prepare and submit a job. The Bot creates a new job working directory, checks out the contents of the pull request, and sets up job configuration data. It then submits the job whilst ensuring that it will run on the CPU microarchitecture needed to correctly build the software package as specified.

Process a finished job. When a job has finished, the Bot processes the result of the job (success or failure). It uses information that was created by a script provided by the target repository of the pull request (`bot/check-build.sh`, see Section 3.3), to update the status record (an issue comment corresponding to a job) on the Git hosting platform (in this case GitHub).

3.3 Interface to Git repositories

The interface between the Bot and the Git repository it is configured to process events for is deliberately designed such that the Bot does not need to be aware of what it builds. Thus, the Bot is very flexible and can be used for different scenarios. We have already used the Bot for building both software packages for the software layer of EESSI, and the compatibility layer of EESSI.

Figure 1: High-level overview of the workflow to add software to EESSI.

Multiple project partners have also successfully employed the Bot in different scenarios, outside of the EESSI context, to further automate the deployment of local system-wide stacks of scientific software.

The job script (provided with the Bot) expects to find the scripts listed below, and executes them in this order. If a script is not found, its execution is skipped. In the future, the behaviour of the Bot can be extended by letting it pick up additional scripts.

1. `bot/build.sh` – builds the software and creates a tarball of all new files.
2. `bot/check-build.sh` – analyzes the result of the build job and produces a block of HTML text that is used by the Bot to update the status of the job in the pull/merge request.
3. `bot/test.sh` – runs tests of the newly built software.
4. `bot/check-test.sh` – analyzes the result of the tests and produces a block of HTML text that is used by the Bot to update the status of the job on the Git repository hosting platform.

3.4 User interface

After creating a pull/merge request to a Git repository (for which the Bot receives events), a user can do the following actions to interact with the Bot

- Send commands to the Bot by creating new issue comments that contain lines with specific commands
- Instruct the Bot to initiate the deployment procedure by setting the label `bot:deploy` for a pull/merge request

Currently, the Bot supports the following commands

```
bot: help           Print usage information for Bot commands
bot: show_config    Show configuration information of the Bot
bot: build [FILTER] Instruct the Bot to submit jobs for CPU microarchitectures, CernVM-FS repositories
                    and Bot instances that match the provided filters
```

3.5 Installation and configuration of the Bot

The GitHub repository [EESSI/eessi-bot-software-layer](https://github.com/EESSI/eessi-bot-software-layer) contains the Bot code, and provides [releases](#) and a [README](#) to set up the Bot.

Currently, the Bot requires a [Slurm](#)-based cluster to which it submits jobs. The most basic tools it needs are [SingularityCE](#) 3.7 or [Apptainer](#) 1.0 and [Python](#) 3.6 or newer versions. The Bot supports several configuration settings to adjust it to different environments and to define its behaviour, e.g., who can trigger actions of the Bot and which software packages

it deploys if multiple have been built, etc. All installation and configuration steps are described in detail in the repository's [README](#). The most important settings to be configured are for which CPU microarchitectures the Bot should run a build job, and how it can ensure that a job gets allocated a compute node with the required CPU microarchitecture. This is achieved by defining architecture-specific job submission parameters in a configuration file.

3.6 Tooling and documentation

Every now and then a build job can fail. At the end of a job, its temporary data on disk – build directories, EasyBuild build logs, data of the installation directory ([fuse-overlayfs](#) data and cached data for CernVM-FS) – is retained in a tarball in the job's working directory. Later, this can be used to reinstantiate the (disk) state of the job in an interactive session to investigate why the job failed. The script [bot/inspect.sh](#) takes a tarball containing the job's state as argument and sets up the environment as it was in the Bot job.

The EESSI documentation contains detailed user-facing information about

- [interacting with the Bot](#),
- [making a contribution to EESSI](#), *and*
- [debugging failed builds](#).

4 Conclusion and outlook

In this report, we briefly introduced the *community contribution policy* (short: Policy) and the *Bot*.

The policy shall enable anyone to make a contribution (adding software) to the EESSI stack. It achieves this through a set of well-motivated requirements every contribution must meet. All software packages that are in the current EESSI software stack comply with the policy. We believe that clearly defining practical requirements that are easy to verify will help its acceptance in the community, and thus lead to a comprehensive software stack that will be a valuable tool/service for many users.

The Bot is a versatile tool to build high-quality software stacks employing the well-known modern *continuous integration / continuous deployment* CI/CD software development practice. It helps implementing the policy and a basic version has been in use for several months. In fact, both the compatibility layer and the software layer provided by the current EESSI repositories have been built with the Bot. For each of the currently 8 supported CPU microarchitectures, version 2023.06 of the EESSI shared software stack contains about 500 software installations (at the time of writing). In total the Bot has run several thousands of jobs. The Bot currently supports the Git repository hosting platform GitHub, and in a future release will be extended to support GitLab-based repositories.

Using the Bot in a production-like environment was instrumental in improving it by adding desired features and fixing bugs. We are committed to continuously improving the Bot based on [already identified needs or issues](#) to make it an even more productive tool for building large shared high-quality software stacks for HPC systems and beyond. In the near future, we will work on making the Bot more robust in handling failures and in enabling more efficient processing of community contributions.

References

Acronyms Used

CI/CD Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
CPU Central Processing Unit
CUDA Compute Unified Device Architecture
EESSI European Environment for Scientific Software Installations
GPU Graphics Processing Unit
HPC High Performance Computing
HTML Hypertext Markup Language
NESSI Norwegian Environment for Scientific Software Installations
SKAO Square Kilometre Array Observatory

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